

Developing a Prediction Model for 7-year and 10-year All-cause Mortality Risk in Type 2 Diabetes Using a Hospital-based Prospective Cohort Study

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Figure S1. Proposed study scenario and application

Figure S2. Flow diagram for study subjects

Figure S3(A). Proportional hazards assumption checking for 7-year follow-up

Figure S3(B). Proportional hazards assumption checking for 10-year follow-up

Figure S4. The (A) Coefficient Progression with selection steps and (B) efficient sequence of cross-validation (7-year model)

Figure S5. The (A) Coefficient Progression with selection steps and (B) efficient sequence of cross-validation (10-year model)

9101(T): training dataset

9101(V): validation dataset

Figure S6. Flowchart for model cross-validation

Figure S7(A). Cumulative all-cause mortality for 7-year follow-up based on 9101 validation subjects

Figure S7(B). Cumulative all-cause mortality for 10-year follow-up based on 9101 validation subjects

Figure S8(A). ROC and AUC for cross-validation at the 2-year time point based on the 7-year follow-up

Figure S8(B). ROC and AUC for cross-validation at the 4-year time point based on the 7-year follow-up

Figure S8(C). ROC and AUC for cross-validation at the 6-year time point based on the 7-year follow-up

Figure S9(A). ROC and AUC for cross-validation at the 2-year time point based on the 10-year follow-up

Figure S9(B). ROC and AUC for cross-validation at the 4-year time point based on the 10-year follow-up

Figure S9(C). ROC and AUC for cross-validation at the 6-year time point based on the 10-year follow-up

Figure S9(D). ROC and AUC for cross-validation at the 8-year time point based on the 10-year follow-up